

Pteronia glauca Boegoekaroo

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.6 meters (height)

Distribution:

Boegoekaroo occurs across the arid interior Karoo regions of South Africa. It occurs from the Namaqualand, through the Great Karoo and Little Karoo, into the Eastern Cape Province.

Importance:

This species is an iconic pasture plant of South Africa's dry interior (the Karoo). Its leaves have a pungent yet pleasantly herbal aroma when bruised. This aromatic flavour is associated with the distinctive taste of Karoo lamb. It is one of the bushes in the sheep's diet considered necessary for producing certified Karoo lamb, as formally recognised in Government Gazette No. 49556.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 87.6 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 14.09 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 4.89 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 79.3%, Duplicated: 20.0%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 2 965.24 kilobases

Contig number: 4 145

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